

**PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF
INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN**

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Annotatsiya: The article outlines the techniques of introducing inclusive educational institutions and preparing future teachers for inclusive education. The essence, objectives and principles of inclusive education of special needs children and adolescents need inclusive education, the role of international organizations in implementing this form of education.

Аннотация: Мақолада таълим муассасаларида инклюзив таълимни жорий этиш ва бўлажак педагогларни инклюзив таълимга тайёрлаш технологиялари ёритилган. Махсус эҳтиёжли болалар ва ўсмирларни инклюзив таълимнинг мазмун-моҳияти, вазифалари, тамойиллари, инклюзив таълимга булган эҳтиёжлар; ушбу таълим шаклини амалга оширишда халқаро ташкилотларнинг вазифалари; инклюзив таълимнинг ҳуқуқий асослари, ресурс педагог ва унинг вазифалари кайд этилган.

Аннотация: В статье рассказывается о внедрении инклюзивного образования в образовательных учреждениях и технологиях подготовки будущих учителей к инклюзивному образованию. Суть, цели, принципы инклюзивного образования для детей с особыми потребностями и выходы, которые имеют инклюзивное образование

Keywords: inclusive education, child with special needs, education, adaptation, doctor-psychoneurologist, pedagogue-defectologist, psychologist, speech therapist

There are still many challenges and barriers to the implementation of inclusive education in the world on a global scale. One of the main reasons is that in many countries the introduction of this education is not specified in government regulations. These include:

- Negative attitude;
- Invisibility in the community;
- Financial problems;
- Physical adaptation;
- Number of students in the class;
- Addiction;
- Discrimination based on gender;
- Emergencies, conflicts and refugees.

Negative attitudes are probably the biggest obstacle to the education of students with special needs in the system of general education institutions. The essence of the problem of negative attitudes is that parents, community members, teachers, staff of general education institutions, even students with special needs in government bodies are reluctant and unwilling to be educated in their own general education institutions. This is due to misconceptions in people about people with disabilities, lack of information about them, students with disabilities growing up in a limited environment, etc. [1.27.b].

The essence of the problem of invisibility in the community is that many students with special needs are often severely concealed by their parents. They are not shown to anyone under house arrest, and no information is given about the disabled child during the registration process. As a result, many students with disabilities are deprived of participation in the community. The lack of any information about them leads them to not attend educational institutions.

Financial problems. In many countries around the world, it is believed that the education of students with special needs in secondary schools is very expensive.

That is why they do not solve the problem of introducing an inclusive education system.

The issue of physical adaptation exists in every country, and at the heart of this problem is the issue of school attendance of students with special needs. When a child with special needs comes to school, he or she faces many problems, such as getting inside the building, moving around the rooms, going to the toilet, and so on. Physical safety and comfort are important in inclusive education.

The problem of the number of students in a class. The large number of students in a classroom in many countries hinders inclusion for students with special needs. In developed countries, the number of students in each class does not exceed 30. However, in less developed countries, it is common for 60-100 children to study in one class.

Addiction problem. This means that most students with special needs are constantly in need of support from others.

The problem with gender discrimination is that boys and girls are not treated equally in education.

Emergencies, conflicts and refugees. Emergencies, conflicts and refugees are not only a cause of disability, but also a factor that deepens the vulnerability of students with special needs. Globally, there are no solutions to this problem. Significant work has been done in the country to train students in need of special assistance in the system of general education institutions. In cooperation with international organizations UNESCO and UNICEF, training seminars and international conferences on inclusive education have been organized.

As a result of the work carried out, the attitude of public organizations to the education of students with disabilities has changed, the attention of parents to students, the interest in learning has increased.

Despite the fact that in Uzbekistan there are specific problems and difficulties in attracting students with disabilities to secondary schools, the organization of education on the basis of integration, it is developing in all regions. Efforts are also

being made to organize other non-traditional forms of education for students with disabilities.

In addition to a certain level of success, there are some issues that need to be addressed:

- Lack of textbooks for parents on the system of education of students with disabilities, the system of inclusive education;
- The system of funding for home schooling of students with special needs is not well established in the field;
- not specified in the state regulations on the introduction of inclusive education;
- Lack of close connection between the school and the families of students with disabilities;
- Issues of providing transportation for students with disabilities to school;
- Poor diagnosis in remote villages;
- Lack of wheelchairs, crutches, hearing aids, glasses, traumatological shoes;
- the state has not fully addressed the problems of vocational guidance, employment;
- Lack of benefits for parents caring for students with disabilities;
- negative attitude of the environment towards students with disabilities;
- Work with students with disabilities is not well organized in the community and the activities of non-governmental organizations are insufficient;
- Insufficient legal knowledge of parents of students with disabilities and ignorance of the benefits provided by the state;
- Insufficient staff for educational institutions;
- facilities are not adapted for students with special needs;
- special education of general education teachers in the system of professional development. retraining is not in demand, etc.

To solve the above problems, the following issues need to be addressed. They are:

In the legal direction:

An article on inclusive education was added to the Law on Education; (September 23, 2020. New edition of the Law on Education. Article 20)

Students and adolescents with disabilities are social and a bill approving correctional pedagogy preparation;

“Approval of the Regulations on Continuing Education for Students and Adolescents with Disabilities in Physical or Mental Development;

Improving the system of continuous inclusive education for students and adolescents with physical or mental disabilities;

Identify a financial resource mechanism that supports inclusive education, its legal protection;

Preparation of proposals on the implementation of the Law on Social Protection of Persons with Disabilities.

In the scientific and methodological direction:

"The concept of inclusive education" developed by LR Muminova, DA Nazarova;

Methodical complexes (program, textbook, curriculum, methodical manual; and recommendations) are created;

Adaptation of the new edition of the STS to inclusive education, as well as curricula for inclusive schools, taking into account the fact that students with disabilities are educated in secondary schools;

A single database of students and adolescents with disabilities in the country, aimed at correctional assistance, has been created on the basis of new modern computer technologies.

In the direction of management:

A variety of relationships with students in need of special assistance a coordination center has been established, uniting organizations and departments; Ensuring interstate multifaceted development; (organizing seminars, conferences, exchange of work experience, publishing magazines, etc.).

The Republican Coordinating Republican Scientific-Practical Center for Social Adaptation and Rehabilitation of Students and Adolescents with Disabilities has been established.

In the direction of school:

Expand the use of financial support and private resources in the implementation of inclusive education;

Make suggestions for studying the material and technical base required for an inclusive school.

Assistance to students with disabilities in the country is carried out in three areas: through the Ministries of Public Education, Health and Social Welfare.

Under the Ministry of Public Education:

The need to identify students with developmental disabilities as early as possible and send them to appropriate institutions is due to the fact that many students with various developmental disabilities study in secondary schools and find it difficult to master the school curriculum. They must be educated and brought up in conditions that suit their characteristics.

Proper selection of students in inclusive schools is one of the most important tasks of the state public education system. It is the responsibility of the selection committees to select and select the students who need to be educated and taught in certain types of inclusive schools. A comprehensive study of the child in all respects can be successful if it is carried out in the course of the child’s activities. The methods and materials used in the study and examination of the child should also take into account their age and individual characteristics. Commission members need to communicate with the child, to better understand his personal qualities. [2; 20.b]

The admission of students to inclusive schools to the inclusive classes is based on the standard regulations of the medical-pedagogical commission and the admission of students with mental and physical disabilities.

The members of the commission are approved by the Department of Public Education. The members of the commission include a doctor-psychoneurologist, pedagogue-defectologist, psychologist, speech therapist. The chairman of the commission is a representative of the department of public education (the

representative of the Ministry of Public Education in the Republican Commission) and the deputy chairman of the commission is a representative of the health department (the representative of the Ministry of Health in the Republican Commission).

Medical research includes ophthalmological, otolaryngological, somatic, neurological, and psychiatric examinations. It is advisable for the commission to conduct a medical examination of the child first.

Methods of examination in the medical pedagogical commission:

1. Medical examination.
2. Psychological examination.
3. Pedagogical examination
4. Speech therapy examination.

After a thorough examination, the child submits an examination report, which includes brief analytical data, clinical, pedagogical, speech therapy examination data, general conclusions and information about other disorders. The child will be shown the type of school recommended, as well as the necessary treatment. The protocol is recommended for kindergarten, inclusive school, where the child is sent. The need for inclusive education stems from the fact that it has the following benefits for society and students with special needs;

- Inclusive education allows students with special needs to always be in the company of their families, neighborhoods and relatives.
- Inclusive education can serve as a catalyst for all to improve the quality of education;
- Placement of students in remote boarding schools prevents them from participating in the life of their home, family and community;
- A child who is far from home, family, parental love, grows up strong, because the family is the main center of education.

It is assumed that the above-mentioned professional information will provide teachers with the necessary amount of special methods of working with students

with disabilities. The type of support a teacher needs is based on his or her specific questions and the specifics of the learning environment. The special teacher also acts as an assistant (assistant) who can work with the student depending on the need and in accordance with the science material. A science teacher can obtain knowledge, skills, and correction techniques from a specialized teacher, and, if necessary, a school teacher can also seek help from other professionals (e.g., representatives of various services, including medical staff, etc.). Resource centers will be responsible for providing inclusive education and managing all participants in the process. The centers are responsible for the quality of integrated child education. They advise teachers, parents and administrative bodies, organize training of secondary school staff, participate in pedagogical councils. The centers provide information to parents and the general public; coordinate the activities of all services to some extent related to solving the problems of students in need of inclusive education in secondary schools; cooperates with local government bodies, institutions, organizations, experts in the field of inclusive education, medical centers and schools. [3; 110.b]

In conclusion, it should be noted that the admission of students with special needs to secondary schools encourages the development of new teaching methods that are more active and involve more students. And the benefit of this is for every child. There is a misconception and attitude towards people with disabilities in society. This may be due to a lack of information about them and the fact that they were educated in closed institutions in special institutions from an early age. Losing or reducing such a relationship is a much more difficult task. But experience has shown that students are more likely than adults to understand differences and similarities. L.S. Vygotsky argues that the social environment is of paramount importance to students with disabilities. Similarly, it likens the development of students with disabilities to a bad plant with roots. “Its thin roots do not match the layers and shape of the nutrient soil. They do not reach the nutrient layers of the soil on their own and enter the dry and toxic layer. “Such a plant could have flourished under the right conditions, but under normal conditions, it withered without reaching

the peak of development." If students with special needs were educated and nurtured together with students with normal development, this would ensure that all students were not discriminated against, realizing that they were children like themselves with disabilities.

Inclusive education is a measure of quality education based on the right to education and emphasis on equality in attendance, and it has a positive approach to the individual learning needs and competitiveness of all students. Inclusive education is child-centered and places the responsibility of adaptation on the education system rather than on the individual child. Inclusive education, together with the general public and other sectors, actively works to ensure that every child, regardless of gender, language, ability, religion, nationality or other characteristics, is encouraged to study with their peers, attend classes and develop their full potential. There is no standard model that defines education as inclusive. Inclusive education allows all students to succeed in school, to participate in lessons on a regular basis.

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